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A comparative study of evolution in translation theories

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Abstract

This study aims to gain insights into how translation has changed in due course and explore different viewpoints betimes on translation. In this context, the turns in translation are investigated, and the universal, social, and political factors that contribute to periodical differences are examined. Although it can be argued that the source text and whatever is transferred to the target text varies according to the text types, translation theories have developed, and some assumptions are predictable about what may change based on varying opinions in the days to come. This study comprises three parts: a) The pioneering names in the field of translation studies in the context of translation from the past to the present are reviewed; b) The social traces of periodic turns in translation are discussed; and c) The findings on possible strategies for the future of translation studies and how society can bring about translation changes.

Keywords: Translations, Society, Newmark, Venuti, Vermeer

1. Introduction

Translation studies contain intralingual translation, interlingual translation, or translation between different sign systems, causing translation studies to show an alteration in defining the translation. In the early years of the development of translation studies, word-for-word translation was in the foreground. Although the literal translation is thought to have been already promoted, Cicero's perspective on translation emphasizes earlier periods in translation studies. "If we go back to the years before Christ, we find that Cicero departed from the dogma that translation necessarily consisted of a word-for-word rendering." (Snell-Hornby, 1995; Martínez González, 2015, p.8). Here, translation is obtained without prior regard to the requests and interests of the target language's audience, and the translator has various responsibilities to be taken in ST. "In source text (ST) oriented translation, the target culture reader is not expected to be as much influenced as the source culture reader." (Tanrikulu, 2017, p. 97).

2. Translation methods

For Peter Newmark, in the pre-linguistics period of writing on translation, the translation debates focused on whether it should be done in the free method or through paraphrasing, "depending on whether the bias was to be in favor of the author or the reader, the source of the target language of the text." (Fengling, 2017, p.32; Newmark, 1981, p. 38) Newmark (1981) emphasizes the importance of the text in translation by elucidating the translation, exposing meaning losses subjected to many factors. Newmark theorized a method and responded to the debate—in a prescriptive manner—by referring to cultural, "factual, aesthetic, allegorical truth, logical and linguistic truth" (Newmark, 2004, p.8) or a set of these factors. Up the mentioned factors, opposing theorems are asserted:

A) Cultural factor

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- a. The translation is a cultural tool, and ST should be modified to adapt to the target culture.
 - b. The translation is a cultural tool, and ST should be translated with minimal changes to be a schema of the paraphernal nation's mentality.
- B) Linguistic factor
- a. The translator rejoices in the author's expressions as much as possible and enriches the target language (TL).
 - b. The translator must avoid the corrupting expressions of the author in TL.
- C) Moral factor
- a. The translator must be committed to the author's every word.
 - b. The translator must be loyal to the spirit of the work.
- D) Aesthetic factor
- a. The translator must transfer the linguistic strangeness of ST to the translation by defamiliarizing and violating TL's conventions.
 - b. The translator should minimize the linguistic inconsistency of ST and make the translation as fluent as possible.

These rulings are prescriptive and have a subjective and valid basis, well accepted by society, but unacceptable in some instances because they contradict each other. However, their validity ultimately depends on social, cultural, and linguistic preferences. Newmark regards culture as "the way of life and its manifestations that are peculiar to a community that uses a particular language as its means of expression" (Newmark, 1988, p. 94), thus, "the greatest obstacle to translation, at least to the achievement of an accurate and decent translation" (Newmark, 2010, pp.172-173). Culture-specific items (CSIs) "as the most problematic area in 'translation studies'" "[are] arising from generic and cultural aspects manifest themselves in the form of CSIs" (Tekalp, 2019, p.295). Kuleli (2020) asserts, "As a result of the analysis based on Newmark's (2010) categorization of culture specific items (CSI), a total of 163 CSIs was found in the source text." (p.649) In Newmark's (2010) translation procedures for CSIs, the main procedures are: "transference of a cultural word, target language cultural equivalent, descriptive equivalent, componential analysis, transonym" (Newmark, 2010, p. 176-177).

Although translation studies have been gradually formed, translation theorists still find themselves limited to general methods. However, the fundamental difference between the theorists is simplified to several factors that impact various texts through objective issues. The transformation of the theoretician's method from prescriptive to descriptive has many implications for translators who are not obliged to follow the dominant method, depending on the reader and the type of text. The selected method is left to the translator, who must choose the appropriate method with a sense of responsibility—although it is sometimes unfathomable.

For Newmark, the first criterion for the text analysis is the purpose, and the translator's first duty is to understand, analyze, and make generalizations about the text before selecting an appropriate translation method. The second criterion is the translator's purpose in questioning whether a) the process fulfills the emotional and persuasive task of ST, b) the translated text leaves the same effect on the reader as ST, or c) the translator properly transfers the cultural elements of ST or not. The third factor is the reader and the setting of the text, and the translator must question the reader's education level, class, age, and gender. The fourth factor is the quality of the writing and the mastery of the text on the subject. If a text is well written and ST is well versed in the subject, the translator must consider the priority of each

change in the author's meaning over the reader's response, assuming that the reader does not need to take an immediate reaction. (Özyön, 2014, p.22)

The old debate on the proper translation method has changed, and contemporary translators emphasize the importance of fidelity, precision, and balance. The ideas of today's translation scholars first show translation's importance and scope in the contemporary democratic era when translation is not limited to scholars and academics and is considered a compound of linguistic, economic, cultural, social, ethnic, and political factors. However, some translators translate all texts invariably without the ought knowledge of the appropriate method. In recent decades, many proposed methods—undoubtedly overlapping to some extent—have caused fundamental changes in the translation perspectives, and “[the] concept of translation shifts is revived and applied to new methods and questions” (Cyrus, 1970, p.98).

While the classic approach to Study of language and translation has been to isolate phenomena (mainly words) and study them in depth, translation studies is essentially concerned with a web of relationships, the importance of individual items being decided by their relevance in the larger context of text, situation and culture. (Snell-Hornby, 1988, p.36)

2.1. Communicative and Semantic methods

Peter Newmark called the communicative and semantic translation methods by questioning whether a translation should remain close to the source language or be free and idiomatic. Newmark, due to the content and writing style of the text, divides language functions into a) expressive, b) informative, c) vocative, d) phatic, e) aesthetic, and f) multilingual functions.

Among these six functions of language, Newmark presents that the expressive, the informative and the vocative are the three chief functions of language use. Therefore, based on the three main functions of language use, Newmark put forward his text-categories: the expressive type, and informative type and the vocative type, and correspondingly, each type correspond to different translation methods. (Cai, 2019, p.175)

In the communicative method, the translator has more freedom in interpreting the text and aims to communicate with the reader. The translator removes the ambiguities and rewrites the text within the framework of TL's syntactic, semantic, and practical conventions. As “most translators have a tendency to couple communicative translation theory with translation practice, in particular its conducting direction toward literature translation practice” (Bai, 2020, p.2) assigns fluency after a conflict between accuracy and fluency. In the semantic method, the translator preserves the form of ST in the translation as far as the syntactic and semantic rules of TL function properly. Here, ambiguity, inconsistency, and the problems of ST in the translation of literary texts reflect the author's perspective and method of expression as the translator chooses accuracy against fluency.

2.2. Formal and Dynamic equivalences

Eugene A. Nida (1964) assigned formal and dynamic equivalences in Biblical translation to develop his theory and “to achieve the maximum functional equivalence” (Wang, 2010; Li, 2021). In dynamic equivalence, the translation creates the same passivity in the reader as well as ST's influence on its audience. TL's reader is taken into account in dynamic equivalence, and the content is translated to make more sense than a direct translation. Thereby, the translator avoids unfamiliar cultural terms in TL, uncovers the hidden information in ST to canonize the content, and chooses a smooth language for translation. Nida utilizes this method in translating the Bible because the purpose is to inform readers and spark their reactions to the holy message. However, this method is also utilized in various

translations as the preface of recent theories in which the reader, the type of text, and the audience's culture are vitally important for ST. For Nida,

In such a translation one is not so concerned with matching the receptor-language message with the source-language message, but with the dynamic relationship, that the relationship between receptor and message should be substantially the same as that which existed between the original receptors and the message. (Nida, 2000, p.129)

In the formal method, the translator transfers the formal features of ST—phrases and the content—to TL and does not assign creativity to the scribe due to the linguistic requirements of TL. Besides, the order of the author's essaying phrases, punctuation marks, and crossing paragraphs is preserved. However, although the sentences are grammatically correct, they may not keep a coherent style. With all its limitations, this method is considered the best for translating texts such as religious manuscripts, in which the translator prefers to keep the author's style. Nida says, "Formal equivalence focuses attention on the message itself, in both form and content... the message in the receptor culture is constantly compared with the message in the source culture to determine standards of accuracy and correctness." (Nida, 2000, p.129)

2.3. TQA model of Overt versus Covert translation

Juliane House (1989/2015) discussed covert translation, in which the goal is authentic translation similar to ST, which is suitable for translating texts without dependency on language, culture, tradition, or history. Instead of translating words independently, the translator recreates the function of ST in TL—which prevails in press and commercials. "An overt translation is required whenever ST is heavily dependent on the source culture and has independent status within it. A covert translation is required whenever ST is not source culture specific." (Barkhordar & Fatemi, 2020, pp.9-10) Simply, "[the] covert translation attempts not to show the translation's essence and spirit through the functional equivalence to create a text as it would act in the source language." (Valizadeh & Vazifekhhah, 2022, p.1377) However, in overt translation, "the cultural characteristics of the source language are protected intentionally, and the source language receptors are not being overtly and directly addressed" (Valizadeh, & Vazifekhhah, 2022, p.1377).

One-off position of some texts in the main language, written for a particular audience or dependent on culture, tradition, or history, needs a determined method for translating— completely perceptible as a translation—through equivalents for the phrases of ST in TL. Considering cultural merits, this method is suitable for translating religious and political speeches and literary texts. For House (2015), "translation quality assessment means both retrospectively assessing the worth of a translation and prospectively ensuring the quality in the production of a translation" (p.2).

2.4. Foreignization and Domestication

Lawrence Venuti played a major role in the cultural turn represented by Susan Bassnett and André Lefevere. Venuti emphasizes the (in)visibility of the translator in translation—focusing on the translator. As Venuti introduces the translator as the primary focal point in translation studies, Schleiermacher—pioneering Venuti—also brought the focus on the translator. Venuti, Bassnett, and Lefevere suggest that the translated text should be viewed as a distinct piece of work from ST and that translation involves both interlingual and cultural aspects. "During the rewriting process, translators must consider both the cultural, linguistic, and literary systems of the source and TLs. They must interpret the source text based on their own experiences and recreate it in the target system." (Abdal, 2018, p. 578) Venuti (1993) says,

Admitting (with qualifications like ‘as much as possible’) that translation can never be completely adequate to the foreign text, Schleiermacher allowed the translator to choose between a domesticating method, an ethnocentric reduction of the foreign text to target-language cultural values, bringing the author back home, and a foreignizing method, an ethnodeviant pressure on those values to register the linguistic and cultural difference of the foreign text, sending the reader abroad. (p.210)

Due to the above considerations, two options emerge: a) the culture of ST is conveyed directly to the target reader, and b) the characteristics of the target culture translate ST. For Yang (2010), “Domestication and foreignization, however, are concerned with the two cultures, the former meaning replacing the source culture with the target culture and the latter preserving the differences of the source culture.” (p.77) In Foreignization, as Venuti (1995) suggested, the translator deliberately violates the linguistic conventions of TL and transfers part of the linguistic features of ST to the translation. This benefits from Schleiermacherian understanding of the optimal method in translation that leaves the author and the reader alone by the translator. Here, “a target text is produced which deliberately breaks target conventions by retaining something of the foreignness of the original” (Shuttleworth & Cowie, 1997, p.59; Yang, 2010, p.77). Thus, “the aim of foreignization is to develop a kind of translation theory and practice to resist the trend of the dominance of TL, so as to give prominence to the difference between the original and the version in terms of language and culture” (Wang, 2014, p.2424).

For Venuti, foreignization is adopted by cultures with no attitude toward learning other languages and cultures—such as the US—in which the dominant method in translation is the localization method, and the translator a) causes cultural shock by following the defamiliarization method; b) does not show absolute adherence to the linguistic and textual conventions of the target culture; c) introduces the cultural interpretations of the source language into the translation text; and d) creates a style that is not fluent and conventional; thus, the reader feels that the text belongs to another language and culture. When examining its function, despite the aim of localization to increase the reader’s proximity to the source culture, translation involves the absorption of both ST and culture. Venuti summarises the scenario as follows:

Translation is the forcible replacement of the linguistic and cultural difference of the foreign text with a text that will be intelligible to the target-language reader. This difference can never be entirely removed, of course, but it necessarily suffers a reduction and exclusion of possibilities—and an exorbitant gain of other possibilities specific to the translating language. (Venuti, 1993, p. 209)

Domestication for Venuti is a common translation method in the pioneering American culture that does not care about other languages and cultures and prefers to evaluate everything in its familiar linguistic understanding. Venuti criticizes domestication due to “an ethnocentric reduction of the foreign text to Anglo-American cultural values” (1995, p.20) because “[by] selecting the domestication method, especially in translating English and the other languages, the translator helps and supports consciously or unconsciously the Anglo-American cultural imperialism. Because this method imposes the English language as superior to others.” (Çekçi, 2020, p.559) The reader, thereby, does not feel that the text is a translation, and the translator a) selects a text for translation that can easily be translated using the domestication method; b) translates the text in a fluent style so that the translation of the text is closed for the reader. Naturally, the translator has to add merits to the text and subtract some from it to create a fluent style that matches the reader’s expectations. Venuti’s proposed domestication method may not seem suitable for American culture due to its linguistic and cultural narcissism and hostility that challenges other cultures. However, choosing the right translation method in other cultures should be fulfilled considering the specific cultural factors of those societies.

2.5. Abusive Translation

For Lewis (1985/2012), inspired by Derrida, a good translation mixture with ST. Translation—based on interpretation—is inevitably expanded compared to ST. Lewis says “abusive translation” pursues “both to violate and to sustain the principles of usage” (Lewis, 2012, p.236). The translator prefers to follow the language of ST wisely and, by going beyond the conventional limits of the language, expresses a new perspective to the native speakers in an unconventional way. The translator changes the common uses of words and highlights the linguistic differences in ST and the deviations of ST from Standards of the source language, using the tools of TL. Moreover, TL is expanded and compensates faithfully for whatever is lost in translation. This method is used to translate texts with linguistic and literary values with interpretive capabilities; their word-for-word translation is very complicated and does not give TL reader a correct impression of ST. For Lewis, only abusive translation can “do justice to contemporary texts that pursue a critique of conventional ‘phallogocentric’” (von Flotow, 1991, p.80).

2.6. Pure and Hybrid translation methods

Katharina Reiss, a founder of *Skopos theory* in Germany, proposes an objective method for translation criticism in *Translation Criticism, Potentials and Limitations* (2000), categorized according to the function. She agrees with the traditional translation theorists and the established balance as the basis of translation—although it is not expected to establish balance at the level of thought, form, and function. She admits two translation methods:

- a) Pure translation method: the audience or the role of the text in the target culture is stable, and the text does not follow an understandable language without the help of explanations and footnotes. Here, the translator seeks to balance ST’s level of thought or form.
- b) Hybrid method: the translator goes beyond linguistic and cultural boundaries and limitations to provide a translation with the same role in the target culture as ST in the source culture.

The criteria Reiss suggests as guidelines for translation criticism do not follow structures of ST but depend on the type of text that clarifies the level of the balance due to the purpose of the translation. (Chen & Zhang, 2020; Demirkıvıran & Göktepe, 2021) Based on the model proposed by the German psychologist Bühler and his proposed functions of the linguistics sign, Reiss assigns three types of texts:

- a) The main role of informative texts is informing, and the choice of language and style is a function of this position. The translator must be faithful to the content when translating reference books, administrative letters, official documents, and university articles; however, the work depends on the prevailing criteria in the target culture.
- b) In expressive texts, the aesthetic element is dominant, and stylistic features are part of the meaning of the texts because they have an aesthetic effect on the reader. The translator must maintain the dominant role of text in the translation and achieve a stylistic similarity by transferring Stylistic features of ST.
- c) In operative texts, the author aims to persuade the readers and make them take action. In these texts, the content and form are a function of the effect that the text is supposed to create on the reader, and the translation creates a reaction in the reader similar to ST. Here, it is sometimes necessary for the translator to change the content or stylistic features of ST. A text may consist of several types, each of which, in each culture, has its conventional features. (Reiss, 1989)

From the point of view of Skopos theory and functionalism, “the end justifies the means” (Reiss and Vermeer, 1984, p.101; Zheng, 2017, p.624). Reiss draws the translator’s attention to the types of texts and their different roles and emphasizes that the translator must be familiar with the linguistic and

cultural standards and conventions governing all genres. Being a writer or a translator is the only way to sneak into people's imaginations with a purpose, like teaching people the facts of politics, motivating the young generation, or giving information. In some cases, we may not achieve this goal due to the translator's mistranslation. For Reiss, "Unintentional changes may arise from the different language structure as well as from differences in translating competence." (Reiss, 1981, p.121) The translators' translation outside their field and not being proficient in a language structure with a different syntax are examples of unintentional communicative differences. The result is an unintentional consequence, which can negatively affect the target reader. Due to sociological and psychological disparities between the source and target cultures, the translator may need to establish some strategies. Reiss's functionalist approach theory emphasizes the translator, who may not always translate effectively, even if the translator or authors follow their original objective. For instance, although Goethe's main objective in writing *The Sorrows of Young Werther* was to shed light on the issues young people face in society, the book surpassed its intended purpose and led to mass suicides rooted in society's psychological and sociological situation.

2.7. Culture-oriented or reader-oriented methods

Hans Vermeer's Skopos theory of purposeful action suggests that translation is not just a linguistic event but a transition of cultures. Therefore, the translator should adopt both languages and both cultures properly. Since translation is a complex cultural act, the translation theorist cannot be satisfied with a purely linguistic understanding. (Şevik et al., 2015, p.190) ST consists of elements to communicate with different readers, and "The Skopos rule...translate/interpret/speak/write in a way that enables your text/translation to function in the situation in which it is used and with the people who want to use it and precisely in the way they want it to function." (Du, 2012, p.2191) Therefore, translation theory should emphasize two major factors: the culture of translation audiences and the role that translation is supposed to play in the target culture, so every translation theory must be based on a theory in the field of culture. The translator's awareness of the role of translation in the target culture leaves the translator's hand free in choosing the method. By extension, Vermeer's theory is based on two principles:

- a) Human action is subject to its purpose.
- b) The purpose changes according to the audience.

Vermeer considers translation an action with a specific purpose, and the translator must determine the purpose of the translation. For Vermeer, translation is subject to the laws of coherence and fidelity. Coherence elucidates the text's compatibility with variations; ST is considered coherent in its own culture, but its word-for-word translation may not follow coherency in the target culture. Besides, due to the law of fidelity—although the translation is subject to the translator's interpretation of the text and the purpose of the translation—the translation is not ultimately completely alien to ST. Rather, there is a relationship between the two coherent texts. In translating texts with a different role in TL, the fidelity between the two texts or the translator's fidelity is maximized. However, in the translation of literary texts, coherence between the translation and ST is no longer a criterion. Here, adherence to ST is a function of the translation goal. If translation suggests the text has a different role in the target culture, there is no need to create coherence between the two texts. The criterion of adequacy of the text is the adaptation of the text to the predetermined purpose of the translation. The reader-centered method Vermeer proposes is opposed by those who consider adherence to ST as the immutable moral law of translation.

The main idea of translation theory is shaped by "purpose," for Hans Vermeer introduced the Skopos theory in 1970. According to him, stakeholders who are editor, compositor, illustrator, or commissioner are significant. The commissioners lead the translator in their translation: "[t]he translator is such an

expert. It is thus up to him to decide, for instance, what role a source text plays in his translational action. The decisive factor here is the purpose, the *skopos*, of the communication in a given situation. (Nord, 1988, p. 9.)” (Vermeer, 2021, p. 192). Vermeer emphasizes that a major part of the responsibility belongs to the translator and the integration of culture in translation proceeds from one language to another. Each translation provides cultural transmission and transfers the text from the source to the target culture. By considering cultural diversity, Vermeer argues that the translator has to be an intercultural communication expert due to an action of intercultural.

A source text is usually composed originally for a situation in the source culture; hence its status as “source text”, and hence the role of the translator in the process of intercultural communication. This remains true of a source text which has been composed specifically with transcultural communication in mind. In most cases, the original author lacks the necessary knowledge of the target culture and its texts. If he did have the requisite knowledge, he would of course compose his text under the conditions of the target culture, in TL! Language is part of a culture. (Vermeer, 2021, p.192)

According to Vermeer, translation has not only a main purpose but also a sub-purpose. This sub-purpose is the translator’s adaptation of the translation according to the needs and wishes of TL’s readers. Accordingly, if TL’s reader is a child, the translator must translate according to TL’s reader’s needs—even if ST does not appeal to children. Translators who decide on a method before the translation aim to make an educational and instructive translation for the child as a sub-objective, and in the meantime, they have to deal with children’s psychology. Thus, Vermeer’s *Skopos* theory is culture-orientated and contains factors translators and interpreters need to consider.

3. Conclusion

A new era in translation in the realm of technology adopts translation studies. Like every other profession, technology has dominated translation and has been impacted positively and negatively. The question is whether machine translation (MT) will replace human translation. However, the translator best understands ST and TL’s cultural values in the societies impacted by their languages. Although MT cannot read the subtext of ST, technology assists in finding terminology, dictionaries, and parallel texts easier and has given translation a new direction. According to Hutchins and Somers (1992), in machine-assisted human translation, the translator’s task is to translate ST using a machine and then rearrange it. Although fully automatic high-quality translation is discussed in the scheme, it is questioned within the translation framework. Translation theory averts new approaches to the translation process, such as intergenerational translation theory/turn in the future. With the evolution of technology over the generations, the lack of intergenerational communication has emerged as a possible debate in translation studies. The variance in word usage between different age groups demands intra-language translation—even in oral discourse—and technology usage among various generations may necessitate the need for intra-language translation. Misunderstandings may arise when a Türk descendant from a generation unfamiliar with technology interacts with a Türk from the new generation who is well-versed in technology. Generation Z clarifies verbal communication, welcoming foreign words into their everyday language due to social media influence. These linguistic disparities could lead to intergenerational translation in the future in the realm of social and cultural issues.

Culture takes center stage not only in literary translations, but even other translations, such as advertising translations, require unique text based on the source culture; e.g., when an advertisement in question is tailored to the expectations and desires of the particular audience. If the brand has global significance, the translation is adjusted, and ST is re-crafted to suit the audience’s expectations. If the advertisement includes visual and audio components, they are translated and adapted to account for cultural differences

across societies. Advertising must be tailored to suit different cultures rather than being translated. (Altay, 1998, p. 41) Moreover, “[although] the products may be identical across cultures, their perceived value varies.” (Altay, 1998, p. 40). Other cultural issues, such as gender inequality, are also impacted by ST while translating.

The translator may translate from a specific approach or include theoretical attitudes as an annotations in the target text. The translator may remain faithful to the point of view of ST and rewrite it by changing expressions using non-sexist discourse until TL reader may come to a different conclusion than ST. The translator may also disclose ST and give TL reader a positive perspective, as “signature on a translation” for Snell-Hornby (2006) “means: this translation has used every possible feminist strategy to make the feminine visible in language.” (p.102) Similarly, in the translation of ST taken from an exploited country into an exploiting country, the positive postcolonial translation strategy increases awareness. “The linking of colonization and translation is accompanied by the argument that translation has played an active role in the colonization process and in disseminating an ideologically motivated image of colonized people.” (El-Daly, 2015, p. 381). However, the effect of postcolonial rewriting may not always be consistent. The translator’s intention and ethical understanding are critical in transferring the content to another culture. Consequently, other societies conscious of colonization within “the colonial power structure” (Abdal, 2018, p. 582) may positively raise their motivation while evaluating TL.

There have been various turning points for translation studies scholars under the theorizing and development of technology, which has enriched translation. Every turn in the translation is characterized by the requirements of the period, and translation is classified by linguistic, cultural, sociological, psychological, and technological turns. In translation studies, the concept of the linguistic turn is language-based, and significant translation scholars such as Nida and Newmark have represented these concepts. Besides, Bassnett and Lefevere have provided a new approach to translation studies as representatives of the cultural turn, which involves creating ST according to cultural characteristics and the target audience’s cultural understanding. When examining translation’s sociological and psychological aspects, it becomes apparent that human beings and society have postcolonial and gender-specific impacts on the translation process. Scholars like Simon, Apter, and Gentzler have contributed significantly to translation studies after technology integration. This study investigated the pioneering names in translation studies in the context of translation theories to display the probable alterations in translational functioning hereupon.

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